

Exploring Live Payload Migrations for MTD in Microservices Architecture

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Abstract—This paper explores the implementation of live migrations within microservices architecture, with a focus on Moving Target Defense (MTD) in the context of cybersecurity. MTD aims to improve system security by introducing changes across multiple dimensions, increasing uncertainty for attackers. Our work dives into container migration techniques within Kubernetes, utilizing two clusters for a redundant deployment. Two payload migration approaches, “kill-first” and “replicate-first,” are proposed, implemented and investigated leading to some preliminary measurement results. The paper assesses the impact of these techniques on microservice applications, specifically their downtime during migrations. Additionally, it discusses security aspects related to container migration.

I. INTRODUCTION

The variety and quantity of cyberattacks observed from July 2022 until June 2023 have risen compared to previous years. These circumstances, combined with the state actor-driven cyberhazards related to conflicts such as the ongoing Russian invasion in Ukraine, lead to further challenges [1]. With the continuous rise of cyberattacks, the need for countermeasures also increases. This requirement is expected to become more critical with the advent of future networks such as 6G or NextG systems. The challenge lies in the dynamic and evolving nature of cyber threats against a fixed target and the need for proactive defense strategies that can reduce the effectiveness of targeted attacks. Traditional security measures generally focus on hardening a system and often fall short in the face of tailored sophisticated attacks, inducing the need for different security approaches.

Assuming that it is impossible to achieve perfect security under these circumstances and, thus, attacks cannot be prevented entirely, a system needs the ability to evade or counter the targeting of a system that happens prior to the attack. One proposed method of combating these threats is the Moving Target Defense (MTD). This concept is commonly compared to the classic “shell game”, where a ball is hidden under one of three shells which then are shuffled. A player must then guess under which shell the ball is located [2]. In this game, the attacker trying to gain access to the system is portrayed by the player, whereas the ball can be seen as an analogy for the targeted system. A more formal definition for MTD given by the US National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) is the following: “MTD is the concept of controlling change across multiple system dimensions to

increase uncertainty and apparent complexity for attackers, reduce their window of opportunity, and increase the costs of their probing and attack efforts.” [3]. This definition proposes a multitude of possibilities regarding the implementation of MTD strategies. One such approach investigated in this work is to devise a way to migrate containers running microservice applications across Kubernetes¹ clusters while preserving their states. Additionally, the downtime of the migrated applications should be as low as possible for clients to stay connected and, preferably, not to perceive any deterioration of the quality of service (QoS).

A microservice is, at its core, a small application that has a single responsibility. Therefore, it is (compared to traditional applications) relatively easy to deploy, scale, and test independently [4]. The microservice architecture therefore describes an architectural paradigm to build an application or a system that is divided into smaller self-sustained microservice applications [5]. These microservices usually run inside containers, which, at their core, are lightweight virtualization instances that use the host’s kernel and have their own memory, instruction set, and networking (similar to virtual machines). Containers are often used in cloud computing as they offer a fast and easy way to be deployed and exchanged in comparison to virtual machines [6], [7].

This work also investigates the security aspects of the above-mentioned container migration problem. While this method could be seen as an evasion maneuver to deny possible attackers access to the system, it could also be effective if the system is already compromised by changing the operational environment and configuration. Both of these aspects are also elaborated in the discussion.

The contributions of this work are inherently related to these technical questions and thus include:

- A streamlined methodology for container migration
- Performance profiling of the proposed methodology
- A discussion of security aspects regarding this method

II. CONTAINER MIGRATION

In the context of Kubernetes and this paper, migration is achieved by successfully transferring the container’s microservice application, its storage data, memory, and CPU state from

¹Kubernetes - <https://kubernetes.io/>

the source to the destination, and this can be done within one cluster from node to node or in a multi-cluster setup from cluster to cluster [8]. There are two types of container live migrations: stateful and stateless. In stateful migrations, maintaining service continuity involves transmitting and synchronizing the container’s state, including runtime in-memory data and other internal state data, between the source and the destination nodes. In contrast, stateless migration is done by restarting the container after copying the container image from the source node to the destination node and does not require transmitting the previous state of the container. If a migration happens during a short amount of time, i.e., some hundred ms, and happens without terminating active network connections, it can be considered a live migration, as the downtime is kept low and is not perceived by clients [9].

1) *StatefulSets and StatefulSet Migration:* In Kubernetes, a StatefulSet is a higher-level abstraction used to manage stateful applications. It is a workload API object that is designed to provide guarantees about the ordering and uniqueness of pods by assigning an ordinal number to the pod’s name compared to the random pod identifier name when a Deployment designed for stateless applications is used. This can be used to deploy StatefulSet pods in an ordered manner across clusters [10]. Each pod within a StatefulSet maintains its unique network identity and can be associated with a Persistent Volume (PV), making it advantageous for stateful workloads such as in environments where stable network identifiers, storage persistence, and ordered deployments are required [11].

2) *Migration Workflow:* As proposed in [10], sequentially moving pods from one cluster to another using Kubernetes StatefulSets is thought to provide a way to migrate stateful services. This approach assumes the transfer of a container’s full state, including data in the memory and in the CPU registers. This work examines and tests this live migration approach to validate and affirm such an assumption. Notably, this method is yet missing in the existing live migration scientific literature because of the novelty associated with the functionalities introduced in the recent Kubernetes versions surpassing v1.27. In the experiments, we additionally deploy a network file system (NFS) in order to create a storage platform that is accessible to both the source and destination clusters. The PVs are mounted on specific subdirectories within this NFS, which, are requested when needed via Persistent Volume Claims (PVCs).

The operational steps proposed in [10] and implemented (with some changes) in this work are the following:

- 1) Deploy a StatefulSet with $x > 0$ replicas (i.e., pods) in the source cluster
- 2) Deploy a StatefulSet with 0 replicas (i.e., pods) in the destination cluster
- 3) Scale down the StatefulSet in the source cluster by 1 (i.e., $x-1$)
- 4) Migrate dependencies, such as PVs and PVCs, from the source cluster to the destination cluster by following these steps:
 - a) Retrieve PVC yaml

- b) Remove specific fields and metadata from PVC yaml
 - c) Redirect the modified yaml data to a file in /tmp/
 - d) Extract PV from the modified PVC yaml in /tmp/
 - e) Remove specific fields and metadata from PV yaml that do not apply to the destination
 - f) Redirect the modified yaml data to a file in /tmp/
- 5) Create PV and PVC in the new cluster by applying the modified yaml files
 - 6) Scale up StatefulSet in the destination cluster by 1, with start ordinal of $x-1$
 - 7) Repeat Steps 3 - 6 for the remainder of pods until the StatefulSet in the destination cluster is scaled to x

III. MIGRATION TECHNIQUES

Following the live migration method previously described, two live migration approaches are further designed and tested, which differ in the order of down/upscaling and the retrievals of the PV/PVC. The implementation of these steps was automated using shell scripts. The underlying scenario is to migrate a pod from one cluster to the other in our testbed as seen in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Migration of a pod and its containers from Cluster1 to Cluster2

A. Kill-First Migration

The kill-first migration aims to simulate a reactive maneuver to counter ongoing attacks on the system. It is oriented on a migration based on CRIU (Checkpoint/Restore in Userspace), which is an open-source tool and set of Linux kernel features that enable the checkpointing and restoring of running processes in userspace. CRIU captures the complete state of a process by freezing it, including its memory, file descriptors, and other relevant information to later restore in the destination [8] [12]. The preserved state can then be restored on a new instance on the same or a different machine [13].

In this work, this migration is implemented in the following way:

- 1) Scale down StatefulSet in the source to 0
- 2) Retrieve PVC and PV information for migration
- 3) Apply PVC and PV in the destination cluster
- 4) Wait for PVC and PV to be ready in the destination
- 5) Scale up StatefulSet in the destination to 1
- 6) Wait for the pod in the destination to be ready
- 7) Continue with the task from before the migration

As this method is primarily seen as a reactive maneuver, it is of great importance that the “application under attack” is shut down as fast as possible. The first step in this migration algorithm is scaling down the StatefulSet, i.e., terminating the application and making it inaccessible. After this move has been performed, information about the state is retrieved and applied to the destination cluster. A new instance mirroring the retrieved state will be initiated in this location.

B. Replicate-First Migration

Unlike the kill-first migration, the replicate-first migration’s primary goal is to keep the application’s downtime as low as possible. It can be seen as an evasive proactive defense against reconnaissance/fingerprinting or potential attacks exploiting a hypervisor’s isolation vulnerability, as in cloud side-channel attacks [14][15]. As the system is not immediately threatened in this scenario, the aim is to keep established connections alive. This method follows the same steps of the kill-first method, only placing Step 1 after Step 4.

C. Are Proposed Techniques Stateful or Quasi-Stateful?

An important question about the StatefulSet migration method proposed in [10] is whether it is genuinely Stateful or not. Essentially, it does not yield genuine stateful migrations considering how it operates. Instead, the performed migrations can be described as “stateless migrations of StatefulSets”. The reason for this is that the container’s state regarding its CPU and memory was not preserved using either approach but recreated using an independently saved state.

IV. PERFORMANCE MEASUREMENTS

A. Experimental Setup

The infrastructure is implemented with OpenStack, a cloud computing platform, with all VMs used as the nodes of the Kubernetes clusters running Ubuntu 22.04.3 LTS. Each cluster contains one master node and two worker nodes. Specific configurations for each virtual machine are detailed in Figure 1. As seen in the figure, the workers feature all the same virtual CPUs (vCPUs), amount of RAM and storage capacity except for Worker1. Furthermore, the two master nodes, MN1 and MN2, oversee clusters Cluster1 and Cluster2, respectively.

Another VM is set up for remote control using `kubectl` to centrally manage and orchestrate both Kubernetes clusters. This node contains all the configuration files, `.yaml`, and `.py` files which are used to setup the microservices and running the applications mentioned in Section IV-B. Additionally, the remote controller VM hosts the NFS, functioning as the shared storage of both clusters, persisting data across them. The open-source project `nfs-ganesha` was used as an NFS. It is a user-mode file server able to deploy NFS v3, 4.0, 4.1, and 4.2².

²NFS-Ganesha: <https://nfs-ganesha.github.io/>

B. Benchmarking Applications Used for Performance Analysis

In this microservice environment, benchmarking applications were developed with different containers specialized to address resource-intensive tasks. These applications were designed to evaluate the migration under different service conditions.

1) *Memory Intensive*: The primary goal is to simulate in-memory workloads within a dedicated container. To achieve this, a script was created that behaves as a simple data generator, writing and reading data into a Redis database. It continuously generates and inserts data with a key and a corresponding value representing the current date and time. Since Redis is an in-memory database [16], the script creates in-memory workload in the respective container.

2) *Disk Read/Write Intensive*: A disk read/write intensive container can be achieved by creating a workload that puts a high demand on the read and write operations performed by a storage device. As MongoDB saves its database on disk, in contrast to Redis in-memory operation, it attempts to achieve a workload onto the disk by constantly writing to it.

C. Metrics

Two metrics were used during the experiments to investigate the migration performance. The parameter *pod downtime d* describes the period (in ms) when a service is not operational in either cluster, i.e., the moment a pod is terminated in one cluster until it becomes available in the other. During this time, the service provided by the pod is unreachable.

The *migration time m* is defined as the duration (in ms) when an application and/or its associated data is being moved or replicated from the source to the destination cluster. This timeframe starts with the initiation of the migration and concludes upon successful completion of the migration process. It is important to note that the migration time includes the service downtime, but may also add other phases involved in moving an application, e.g., getting necessary parameters at the source and setting them up at the destination environment or the pod going through a graceful shutdown. Thus, *m* is larger than or equal to *d*.

D. Experimental Results

1) *Memory Intensive Kill-First Migration*: Figure 2 shows the migration duration and pod downtime, respectively, sorted from low to high. As expected, the difference between the time it takes to perform the migration and the time the pod is unavailable is relatively close, with the pod downtime being on average 0.132s lower compared to the migration time.

The data also shows volatility in the time it takes to migrate the pods from one cluster to another as well as the pod downtime, ranging from around three seconds to 28. The corresponding histogram in Fig. 3 also shows that most migrations range from five up to 15 seconds. By turning the load generation off, the migration is performed within a timeframe of five to ten seconds. This indicates a correlation between the time it takes to terminate a pod gracefully with K8s and the processes running inside it.

Fig. 2. Memory intensive kill-first migration measurements, sorted from lowest to highest values regarding migration duration and pod downtime

Fig. 3. Histogram of different migration techniques.

One hypothesis for the high migration time of up to 28 seconds is that every time a migration was performed, the Redis image used had to be pulled from Dockerhub, which further increased migration time. This process involves building up a connection to Dockerhub, authentication, downloading the corresponding image, and application to the cluster.

2) *Memory Intensive Replicate-First Migration*: In Fig. 4, it can be seen that the pod downtime is in every case lower than the actual duration of the migration, on average by around 2.6 seconds or 28.2%. This is expected as the migration, as described in Section III-B, terminates the pod and then replicates it again on another machine.

The histogram in Fig. 3 shows that migration times of more than 15 seconds are unusual. As the correlation between pod downtime and migration time seems to be linear, the same applies to pod downtimes. This does not change when the load generation is shut down. While the new replica pod is starting in the destination cluster, the original instance is turning off. In some cases, the replica is ready for connection as soon as the original instance is killed, leading to pod downtimes of under one second. In other cases, the replica is not yet ready for requests and therefore prolongs the downtime.

Similar to the measurements for memory intensive kill-first migration, the time between the fastest and slowest migrations is significant (from 0.2 seconds to 22 seconds). The same hypothesis as before on the image downloading from

Fig. 4. Memory intensive replicate-first migration measurements, sorted from lowest to highest values regarding migration duration and pod downtime

Fig. 5. Disk intensive kill-first migration measurements, sorted from lowest to highest values regarding migration duration and pod downtime

Dockerhub applies here as well.

3) *Disk Intensive Kill-First Migration*: Similar to the memory-intensive migration experiments, the pod downtime and overall migration time are close to each other with a difference of 0.178 seconds on average. The scatterplot in Figure 5, like in the previous two sections, shows a significant variation between maximum and minimum migration times, with potential factors like networking issues or delays due to image downloading possibly contributing. However, when looking at the histogram, it is apparent that most migrations are performed within a timeframe of a maximum of ten seconds. However, a seemingly random distribution is observed when the load generation is not running.

E. Performance Overview

The performance profiling of present migrations offers a focused examination of how the proposed methods handle various scenarios, as shown in Table I. Evaluating the measured differences in average migration time \bar{m} and pod downtime \bar{d} provides insights into the behavior of the migration strategies. Please note that kill-first migration was conducted on both memory and disk read/write intensive containers, replicate-first was not possible in the disk read/write intensive application. The reason for this is the MongoDB instance, which does not allow another instance to be connected with the same NFS at the same time in the current setup.

TABLE I
PERFORMANCE MEASUREMENTS

Container	Migration Mode	\bar{d} (ms)	\bar{m} (ms)
Mem. Intensive	Kill-First	10'545	10'647
Mem. Intensive w/o Load	Kill-First	8'932	9'090
Mem. Intensive	Replicate-First	6'399	8'914
Mem. Intensive w/o Load	Replicate-First	5'408	8'615
Disk RW Intensive	Kill-First	9'005	9'183
Disk RW Intensive w/o Load	Kill-First	9'601	9'729

From the experiments, we conclude that the replicate-first migration strategy exhibits shorter migration durations and is less susceptible to the augmented read/write load in comparison to its kill-first counterpart. Moreover, this method contributes to reduced migration downtime, resulting in an average increase of 40% in service availability during the migration process.

V. SECURITY ASPECTS

As mentioned in the introduction, the migration of containers can be seen as either an evasive maneuver to prevent attacks or as a reactive maneuver to deny them entirely. With the underlying goal of users ideally not perceiving any downtime during a migration, a replicate-first migration seems to be the way to preserve connections and changing the environment at the same time when using one instance only. Creating a replica in a safe environment and redirecting explicitly authorized connections could provide additional security. As replicate-first migrations would primarily be stateless evasive techniques, redirection could happen without checking if the application is infected, as the default container image is used to start the new replica. For stateful services the kill-first approach is necessary, introducing a conflict between the goals of security and connection liveness/QoS.

If an application is allowed to have downtime, a kill-first migration would be the safer choice. As it terminates the pod at the start of the migration process, any connection established, whether authorized or not, is dropped. This gives potential attackers less time to do reconnaissance as well as data collection in case of a breach. On the other hand, if the service is already infected, the transfer of the service state might induce to the migration of the malware/infection along with the service.

Using more resources to run multiple instances simultaneously could provide a way to keeping connections alive no matter the migration method used while at the same time performing complex migrations.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this work, a methodology for container migration based on Kubernetes StatefulSets and its performance profiling is provided. We conclude that this type of migration is not fully stateful as opposed to using CRIU, making it unsuitable for some types of applications. A discussion of the security aspects of using this method for MTD was also done. A critical

open research question is how the proposed migrations can be modified for live migration. A greater exploration of the performance implications associated with live migration using CRIU, particularly when applied to fully developed applications, holds the potential to produce even further insights. Moreover, introducing monitoring of CPU, RAM, and disk states as additional metrics could offer a better understanding of the systems during migrations.

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